

Say Yes to Life: Organ Donation, Public Health, and the Power of Black Women's Advocacy

KIA WHITE, MPH

ABSTRACT

This article explores the critical role of Black women in advancing health equity through organ and tissue donation. By examining the partnership between LifeNet Health and the Black History Museum & Cultural Center of Virginia, the article highlights how culturally rooted initiatives can dismantle barriers of mistrust and misinformation. It underscores the urgency of addressing chronic illnesses disproportionately affecting Black women; such illnesses include heart disease, chronic kidney disease, and diabetes, which necessitate transplants. The article advocates for framing donation as a public health imperative, emphasizing the impact of medical racism and implicit bias on transplant access and outcomes. It calls for community-based efforts to foster trusted conversations and positions Black women as leaders in health advocacy. Actionable steps for promoting health equity are provided, emphasizing the importance of registration, education, and community engagement. Ultimately, the article portrays organ and tissue donation as a radical act of love and legacy, essential for the fight for health equity.

INTRODUCTION

In 2021, LifeNet Health created the One Hero project to address the need for greater organ and tissue donation awareness and

registration in the Black community. However, raising awareness and encouraging action among Black Americans was only one aspect of the resolution. If any progress was going to be made in changing the attitudes and generational beliefs pertaining to donation, a discussion regarding the lack of trust in the medical system and how that may pose as a barrier to saying yes to donation was not only something that needed addressing, but it was also imperative to approach these narratives with cultural sensitivity and humility (LifeNet Health 2025).

THE BARRIERS TO DONATION IN THE BLACK COMMUNITY

Throughout history, medical mistrust among Black people, particularly Black women, is rooted in lived experience. The continued use of Henrietta Lacks's cells without authorization highlights the ongoing ethical issues of patient mistreatment in medicine (Wolinetz and Collins 2020).

Fair treatment continues to be a present-day problem. Maternal health is a critical area where Black women continue to face disproportionately high rates of death and illness. Compared to other races, Black women face a disproportionately high risk of pregnancy-related death, regardless of socioeconomic status (Hoyert 2024). This highlights systemic inequalities and increases concerns about how Black women are treated in healthcare.

Disparities in Black maternal mortality rates compared to other races highlight the need for further improvements.

The COVID-19 pandemic amplified longstanding disparities in healthcare access and trust. For Black communities, in-person registration events, often hosted at churches and cultural events, were disrupted. The Department of Motor Vehicles, where over 90% of people make the decision to become a registered donor, was shut down or limited to appointment-only visits (Donate Life America 2025). Hospital visitation limits complicated family conversations about end-of-life care. Pandemic-related fears around healthcare interactions may have deepened mistrust, further deterring donor registration. The decision to register or donate a deceased loved one's organs or tissues has been complicated by the healthcare system's unfair treatment. However, the need for organs in the Black community is great. Health disparities prominent among Black women, unfortunately, seem to increase the likelihood of an organ transplant.

BLACK WOMEN'S INCREASED SUSCEPTIBILITY TO NEEDING A TRANSPLANT

The lack of access to healthcare and early intervention could decrease a Black woman's chances of becoming a waiting list candidate and receiving a lifesaving transplant. Some of the chronic illnesses that may require a transplant are diabetes, heart disease, and renal failure.

Black women experience a higher incidence of chronic diseases that may lead to the need for transplants. Black women are more likely to be diagnosed with heart disease and die from it compared to women of other racial backgrounds (Ogunniyi et al. 2022). Chronic kidney disease, a predominant cause for transplants, affects Black people at nearly four times the rate of White people (Ng et al. 2020). Diabetes, often leading to kidney failure, is more prevalent among Black women than other races (Office of Minority Health 2024). These conditions are exacerbated by the stress of systemic racism. Despite the pressing need, the rate among Black Americans saying

“yes” to donation remains disproportionately low (James-Conterelli et al. 2023).

While organ transplants receive considerable attention, tissue donation is just as crucial. Donated skin aids burn survivors in healing, while donated heart valves, veins, tendons, and bones restore mobility, function, and life (Donate Life America 2025). Birth tissue is even used in reconstructive procedures. There are about 2.5 million tissue transplants performed each year, and approximately 58,000 tissue donors (Donate Life America 2025). The contribution of one tissue donor can enhance the lives of 75 or more people (Donate Life America 2025). Organ and tissue donation must be framed not just as a personal decision, but as a public health priority.

CURATING SAFE SPACES FOR BLACK WOMEN LEADING IN HEALTH EQUITY

For many Black women to feel comfortable having an open dialogue about organ and tissue donation, an environment in which their voices are not only heard but respected must be cultivated. This concept was implemented in the One Hero campaign (onehero.lifenethealth.org) through the One Hero Show podcast, participation in hair salon and barbershop talks, LifeNet Health's partnership with the Black History Museum of Virginia, and community-based initiatives such as back-to-school events and food drives.

The One Hero Show, a podcast featuring two Black women transplant professionals as hosts, as well as healthcare providers and community leaders, addressed issues of health equity in healthcare and misconceptions surrounding donation. Having a platform to curate conversations around the subject provides a culturally relevant solution to create dialogue around a topic that is often not discussed around the dinner table (LifeNet Health 2025).

When LifeNet Health partnered with the Black History Museum & Cultural Center of Virginia, the initiative transcended beyond donor registrations and awareness; it embodied a profound act of changing the narrative. The One Hero campaign anchored the discourse on organ and tissue donation within a context

of deep cultural and historical significance for Black communities. This initiative facilitated dialogues within trusted spaces, aiding in dismantling entrenched barriers of mistrust and misinformation (UNOS 2024).

The community-based outreach efforts were implemented based on the needs assessment conducted for the One Hero priority population. Some of the top necessities included food and school supplies. LifeNet Health was not only present at these back-to-school events and food drives, but they were sponsors and provided backpacks and meals for families during the holidays. What made these outreach strategies effective was the environment that was created in response to fulfilling and addressing community needs. These actions helped staff build relationships and trust with community members and leaders, which positioned LifeNet Health as a compassionate community resource. There was a 19% registration increase in the areas where the One Hero interventions were implemented (UNOS 2024).

BLACK WOMEN: LEADERS IN RESTORATION AND LEGACY

In many Black families, women are the decision-makers, the caregivers, and the advocates. From the matriarchs who read discharge instructions to those negotiating with insurance companies, they are the architects for building structures and transformation. This leadership extends to donation. When Black women choose to register, learn more, or share information within their circles, it creates a ripple effect. These acts of care, rooted in information and action, contribute to a legacy of health advocacy.

There are actionable steps Black women can take to catalyze health equity in donation. This transformation starts with conversations, decisions, and bold choices in everyday spaces. The first step is to take the lead and consider becoming a registered donor. The registration process can occur at the Department of Motor Vehicles, online at your local state registry site, or at the national registry site (RegisterMe.org). Discuss your wishes with family, mentors, and spiritual leaders. Families may feel more confident in their donation decision

when they have insight into their loved ones' end-of-life wishes. Partner with your local donation organization to host a culturally rooted activity within your community. This activity can be a donor drive, sports event, health expo, luncheon, cookout, or a block party, art show, poetry slam, or even an open mic night, to name a few. Use your voice. Representation matters; by becoming a donation ambassador, you can educate and advocate at church functions, sorority events, book clubs, or family reunions. If you have influence or a large platform—whether it is social media, a podcast show, a radio show, or television—spread the message regarding donation by sharing posts from a reputable organ donation organization or inviting guests who have an empowering testimony about donation to share their story.

CONCLUSION

A new beginning, a legacy of life, is symbolized by the selfless act of organ and tissue donation; it is a subject often thoughtfully considered during discussions about end-of-life care. Lives are saved, health is restored, and hope is given because of donation. This act is both radical in nature and a demonstration of love and legacy. Black women have historically been the first to respond to needs, whether at the bedside or on the front lines of social change. In the pursuit of health equity in donation, our voices are not merely powerful—they are indispensable.

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